

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE EXTENSION/TWIST COUPLING IN ROTATING COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

The aim of this study is to characterize the extension/twist coupling (ETC) of composite plate laminates when submitted to axial loading. ETC is achieved by using an antisymmetric lay-up of off-axis plies. In laboratory configuration, extension can be induced by a quasi-static tensile loading or by the centrifugal force of a mass. Rotating tests present the major advantage to offer a high fidelity with the in-service environments of composite components in rotating applications. In the past, several experimental set-ups were designed and developed to characterize ETC in laminates [1-3]. Most of the static tests were performed on bi-axial machines. The tensile load was applied with a free rotation, which makes the twist able to occur in the laminate [3-5]. Analytical and finite element models were also developed by Armanios et al. [6] in order to quantify twist rate in ETC laminate as a function of tensile load. In agreement with experimental observations, modelling results pointed out a non-linear relationship between twist rate and tensile load. This non-linear behaviour originates from geometrical considerations.

This work proposes a new experimental set-up able to accurately determine twist of ETC composite laminates under rotation using non-invasive techniques. These include laser and optical-based methods and also wireless telemetry systems for strain gage measurements.

In rotating tests, aerodynamic forces have to be minimized in order to avoid the induced instabilities and the unwanted loads in the plate and to ensure the relevance of the measurements. To minimize aerodynamic forces, authors in literature developed experiments in a rough vacuum chamber [1, 3]. Working in such conditions is particularly intricate and time-consuming when sophisticated techniques

for twist measurements have to be combined. Therefore the approach adopted in this work consists in minimizing the speed of the air on the plate (Fig.1).

Using this experimental set-up, significant twist rates were measured in ETC plates at the ultimate speed of the rotary drive system. Experimental results are compared to numerical results computed using non-linear FE model.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief description of the experimental set-up and of the twist measurement procedure. In section 3 the FE model is described. Section 4 presents and compares the results obtained using both experimental and numerical approach.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Extension/twist coupling laminate

Tested plates are made of composite materials with a stacking sequence which results from an optimization work to maximize twist in laminate and prevent it from any damage. Antisymmetric orientation distribution keeps away from any other mechanical coupling.

2.2 Rotary drive system

Fig. 1 shows the whole experimental set-up.

Fig. 1. Snapshot of the rotating test bench with measurement devices

As shown in Fig. 2, two laminates located at 180° with respect to one another are clamped to the rotor shaft of a DC brushless motor. Rotation speed is estimated during experimentation by a capacitive sensor.

Masses are positioned at each extremity of both plates to produce an extra centrifugal force and increase plate twist. These masses also support the pattern and the grating used for optical-based measurements.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the rotating parts without the polystyrene disk.

To reduce the speed of the air on the plates and thus preventing them from aerodynamical forces (drag and lift) and disturbances, plates were placed inside an enclosure made of a polystyrene disk, as shown in Fig. 3. Crucial numerical simulations and

experiments were performed before running real tests in order to ensure safety and dynamic stability of the system.

Fig. 3. Polystyrene disk enclosure

The disk also prevents the plates of any major bending, induced by the masses, when the motor does not rotate. When the rotation starts and the speed increases, the centrifugal forces grow, the masses take off and the plates are straightened: from this moment the ETC can be characterized.

2.3 Twist measurement

Two optical-based techniques and an extensometric one were used to determine the twist rate as a function of rotation speed.

2.2.1 strain rosettes

In-plane strains and curvatures were recorded during tests using regular delta strain gage rosettes with a telemetric wireless system (KMT-MT32).

Strain gages were glued on the top and bottom surfaces of the laminates. As a result, the 2D strain tensor can be measured on both surfaces. Middle surface strains and curvatures of the plate can be determined according to the Classical Laminate Theory [7]. Eq. 1 links strains on the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate with mid-surface strains ϵ_x^0 , ϵ_y^0 and γ_{xy}^0 .

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x^0 \\ \epsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{z^+} + \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{z^-} \right) \quad (1)$$

z^+ and z^- are the upper and lower altitudes of the plate.

Curvatures are determined using Eq. 2.

$$\begin{pmatrix} k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{(z^+ - z^-)} \left(\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{z^+} - \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix}_{z^-} \right) \quad (2)$$

The k_{xy} curvature (in $[m^{-1}]$) relates the twist along the first direction of the plate. It can be converted in a more suitable quantity, named twist rate Θ in $[^\circ.m^{-1}]$, according to the following equation:

$$\Theta = \frac{-90}{\pi} k_{xy} \quad (3)$$

To avoid the use of a rotating collector, a wireless telemetry system was preferred in this work. Therefore, the six strain gages of the two rosettes were conditioned by a whole KMT multi-channel telemetry system. It includes a lithium battery, signal condition modules, an encoder, a multiplexer, a controller and a HF transmitter. The maximum acquisition frequency is 95 Hz.

All these modules were positioned on the bottom of the polystyrene disk, close to the main rotor shaft, in order to minimize imbalance induced by these additional masses.

The two following paragraphs describe the twist determination using optical-based measurements of masses rotation.

2.2.2 laser beam diffraction

A diffraction grating was stuck on one of the masses as shown in the schematic representation of the laminate in Fig. 2. Fig. 4 shows the principle of this method with the grating, the monochromatic laser beam and the first order diffracted laser beams.

Fig. 4. Laser beam diffraction through a grating

The position of the diffracted laser beams are recorded on a screen versus time.

The rotation of the mass due to ETC in laminate during operation induces a rotation (as a function of the x-direction) of the two first order diffracted laser beams. The rotation angle is then measured using the line passing through the two points of the laser on the screen (Fig. 5 and 6).

Fig. 5. Snapshots of the laser screen. a) initial time (with no speed).and b) rotated time (high speed rotation)

Fig. 6. Orientation identification with laser spots

An algorithm was developed to locate the laser spots in the pictures and calculate the angle θ .

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{z_r - z_l}{y_r - y_l} \right) \quad (4)$$

where (y_l, z_l) and (y_r, z_r) are the coordinates of the left and right points.

Considering the power of the laser (4.5 mW), there is no need to accurately trigger the camera to obtain contrasted pictures. So, the time of exposure is started with a delay estimated from the rotation speed.

2.2.3 Line pattern rotation

The other mass was covered with a printed line pattern. A picture of this mass in motion is done at different times in order to determine the rotation of the line pattern.

A CCD Ueye camera was used with a telecentric lens. This one minimizes barrel distortion and makes settings easier in comparison to a regular one. This camera is triggered by the capacitive sensor signal. A pulse is generated when the mass passes in front of the lens. At this specific time, a ringlight releases a large amount of energy in a short period to illuminate the line pattern during the exposure time of the CCD sensor.

This whole apparatus prevents pictures from blur effect and improves their sharpness. Snapshots in Fig. 7 were recorded using this method. Change in the orientation of this line pattern allows the rotation of the mass to be determined.

Fig. 7. Snapshots of the line pattern glued on the external faces of the mass.

a) initial time (with no speed). b) rotated time(high speed rotation)

The method applied to determine this rotation is the Radon transform which is often used in medical application to shape recognition [8]. The Radon transform is an integral transform consisting of pixel values over straight lines. A straight line of the pattern is then converted into a point in the Radon space. Fig. 8 gives an illustration of it with the computation on a line defined with the couple (ρ, α) . α is the orientation of the perpendicular and ρ the distance from the origin.

Fig. 8. Calculation of the Radon transform

An example of this transform for our pictures is represented in Fig. 9 in which black and white areas correspond to the line pattern in the original picture. Their locations indicate the orientation of the fringes.

Fig. 9. Radon transform of a picture similar to the Fig. 7b

Intensity of the Radon transform is normalized. 1 value represents white pixels, 0 value black ones. The membership of a pixel in the Radon' space to the line pattern was determined using intensity criteria described in Tab. 1.

picture space	criteria	Radon space
black lines	$R(\rho, \theta) < 0.2$	black pixels
white lines	$R(\rho, \theta) > 0.8$	white pixels
other directions	$0.2 < R(\rho, \theta) < 0.8$	gray pixels

Tab. 1. Distinction criteria used to identify line orientation

A filter keeps only black and white pixel into consideration which represents black and white fringes. A sum is then made over the ρ direction for

each θ value (Fig. 10). This distribution curve reveals a maximum for a specific rotation angle, representing the line pattern orientation with respect to the x-direction.

Fig. 10. Identification of the rotation angle from the discriminated Radon transform

2.4 Loading path

During experiments, the plates were submitted to a ramp with a constant increase of the rotation speed as a function of time. After this ramp, a dwell of about 30 seconds was applied with a constant speed. At last, a second ramp with a constant decrease in speed is applied. This loading path is useful to check the reversibility of the ETC phenomena. In-plane strain and masses rotation were measured at the rotation frequency during the test.

3 Finite element model

A FE model was built to understand and quantify the twist rate of the rotating plate as a function of speed with respect to experiments.

The mesh in Fig. 11 was used to solve this problem with a finite element based code. The plate was discretized using 3D-solid elements with 8 nodes. A regular mesh was used with 8 elements in the width, about one hundred in the length and only one per ply in the thickness. The plate was clamped at one extremity and a concentrated mass was applied at the other extremity. A centrifugal acceleration field consistent with the experimental rotation speed was applied to generate inertial loads.

Fig. 11. Volume mesh of the laminate used for the finite element method resolution

Simulations were made with Samcef software. The use of the Mecano module allowed the geometric non-linearity of the ETC phenomena to be taken into account.

Displacements of nodes belonging to the middle plane were extracted from the computation and processed to determine the rotation at each section of the laminate. The derivative of this rotation distribution represents the twist. Transversal and longitudinal strains were also recorded in order to be compared with experimental results.

4 Results

4.1 Masses take-off at low speed rotation

As aforementioned and as described in Fig. 12, the masses take off and the plates straighten when the rotation speed reaches a threshold value, denoted ω_t .

Fig. 12. Mass take-off problem

The altitude of the mass was monitored as a function of the rotation speed using the line pattern system (Fig. 13). This figure clearly shows the take-off speed threshold.

Fig. 13. Determination of the take-off speed using mass altitude measurement

Twist is highly disturbed by this take-off phenomenon. Below the speed threshold, interface friction between masses and polystyrene disk hinders the mass rotation (Fig. 14). While the twist rate is reversible as a function of the rotation speed above the speed threshold, a large difference in the twist behaviour is observed below this threshold value. In this figure, the twist rate is determined using the in-plane strain measurements.

Fig. 14. Masses take-off perturbations on twist

In next parts, only the twist behaviour observed above the speed threshold will be considered.

4.2 Mass-rotation based technique

To estimate the scattering in rotation measurements involved by experimental techniques, the same laminate was submitted several times to the same loading path (LP). The laminate was also tested on the two possible locations of the test bench (0° and 180°), and by consequence with the two different optical-based techniques. Results of these trials are shown in Fig. 15.

A relatively good repeatability is observed for each technique, above the speed threshold. Experimental results are also in good agreement with the finite element model.

Fig. 15. Mass rotation as a function of speed for the same laminate

A slight gap between the laser and the pattern measurements is also observed. The rotation difference is constant as a function of the rotation speed. This can be explained by the extra-extension caused by the extra-mass of the grating.

The masses rotation can be further used to estimate the global twist of the plate (Eq. 5). In this calculation, the rotation of the laminate cross-section at each extremity is known and the rotation distribution is supposed linear.

$$\Theta = \frac{d\theta(x)}{dx} = \frac{\theta(L) - \theta(0)}{L} \quad (5)$$

This hypothesis of linearity is corroborated by numerical results. Indeed, Fig. 16 depicts the distribution of cross-section rotation. The relationship is clearly linear with small variations in the clamping areas.

Fig. 16. Simulation of the rotation repartition along x-direction at a high velocity

This hypothesis is verified because the mass at the end of the laminate generates an almost uniform tensile stress in the specimen length and width and also because the plate is long enough to minimize clamping effect in the working length.

The twist behaviour extracted from the mass rotation measurements was then compared to the one identified using in-plane strain measurements.

4.3 In-plane strains based technique

In-plane strains and curvatures measured during tests are respectively shown in Fig. 17 and Fig. 18.

In Fig. 17, experimental results are also compared to the numerical simulations. As expected and as predicted by modelling, shear strain γ_{xy}^0 is negligible during test. On the contrary, longitudinal and transverse strains (ϵ_x^0 and ϵ_y^0) vary significantly as a function of the speed rotation. Experimental results are in a quite good agreement with the numerical ones.

An offset exists on transversal strains which can be caused by the too large width of the gage compared to the plate one. This can be attributed to the free edge effects in composite laminate.

Fig. 17. Typical in-mid-plane strains versus rotation speed

Fig. 18 shows the evolution of the laminate curvatures during an experiment. As expected, bending curvatures are particularly small in comparison to the torsion one. The k_{xy} curvature represents plate twist at the location of the strain rosettes.

Fig. 18. Typical curvature versus rotation speed

4.4 Comparison of twist measurement techniques

Fig. 19 summarizes the whole study with a comparison of the twist resulting from the different experimental techniques and modelling.

All the experimental techniques are sensitive to the mass take-off. They are also able to accurately measure the significant twist exhibited by the laminates over the threshold speed.

This results combination gives an overview of the experiment and the efficiency of the twist exposed by this laminate with this bench.

Fig. 19. Twist of the laminate versus rotation speed

Although it is based on an assumption of linearity, the twist determined using mass rotation-based techniques is in a better agreement with the numerical simulations than the in-plane strain base technique.

Twist measured with strain gage rosettes presents the same slope in the twist-speed diagram, but with a constant shift. This could be attributed to the initial twist of the plates. Indeed, strain gages are glued on a theoretically flat specimen. In reality, an initial twist exists. We determined the 3D initial shape of the laminates using an another experimental technique after curing. It was obvious that laminates exhibit an initial twist induced by residual stresses. These results will be published in a forthcoming paper. This initial twist can be reduced with specific stacking sequence [9], but small defects during lay-up process always bring local strains in plates, which penalize strain-based techniques.

5 Discussion

Results points out that the classical mass take off problem only happens at low speed. Accurate and relevant measurements can be performed above this threshold speed.

A good correlation between both experimental measurements and FE simulations was observed.

Mass rotation-based measurements showed a good repeatability and have successfully quantified the twist behaviour of plates.

They were also well-correlated to strain-based measurements. Results also presume that this technique is highly influenced by the initial curvature of the plate.

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